

STUDY OF NANOSTRUCTURED Ni/CeO₂ CATALYSTS PREPARED BY COMBUSTION SYNTHESIS IN DRY REFORMING OF METHANE.

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Abstract.

This work reports the study of several catalysts of Ni/CeO₂ for dry methane reforming process ($\text{CH}_4 + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{CO} + 2\text{H}_2$). The use of Ni as active phase is highly preferred, due to its availability, high activity and low cost, although its main lack is the coke formation on the surface of Ni metal particles, resulting on a severe deactivation. Nevertheless, it has been proposed that if Ni particles are highly dispersed on the oxide serving as support, coke formation could be diminished. Here we report a new synthesis method that allows a simple, effective and fast way to prepare Ni/CeO₂ catalysts, in a wide range of metallic loadings, resulting in all the cases in well formed NiO crystallites with sizes in the range of 12-18 nm. The use of CeO₂ as a support has been based on its massive use in TWC catalysts formulations, where is recognized to activate CH₄ and lower hydrocarbon dissociation. Moreover, CeO₂ has been reported to have an intrinsic activity in the CH₄ reforming reaction. Besides the metallic loading, several factors that control the preparation method of the catalyst have been varied, in order to optimize their performance. Most of the catalysts prepared show activity and selectivity values close to thermodynamic ones, maintaining a good stability on long periods of time and severe conditions. Nevertheless, formation of some carbon nanofibers has been observed, what could result in a drawback for their application at large scale.

Keywords: Methane reforming, H₂ production, heterogeneous catalysts, nanoparticles.

Introduction:

Nowadays, due to the progressively dependence to petroleum and the recent increases in the price of this product, many analysts coincide that we are on the vicinity of a “Hydrogen” era, and that this energy vector will gradually replace in next decades many of the uses of fossil fuels, specially, in areas such as transportation [1,2]. In fact, analysis of “National Hydrogen Program” in USA predicts that in 2025 about 10% of total energy consumption will be based on this fuel [3].

Hydrogen is nowadays recognized as a flexible and environmentally friendly energy vector, and its potential lies not only in the substantial reduction of greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions (and the concomitant quality air improvement), but also in its ability to provide a safe energy supply, with special incidence in transport sector.

When environmental and economic costs for hydrogen production are evaluated, not only production phases should be considered, but all the steps, in what have been called “from the mine to the wheels”. In this context, it should be remarked that nowadays only hydrogen production from methane reforming is economically competitive, and this is expected to maintain at short and medium time. In addition, this process is also the second more environmentally respectful, being only passed by the water electrolysis when electricity is produced from renewable energies [4,5].

Today, there are well developed methods to produce H₂ from natural gas (which its principal component is methane), such as *Steam Methane Reforming* (SMR). These methods account for ca. 95% of the H₂ produced in USA and 50% of the total H₂ produced worldwide.

Steam Methane Reforming (SMR) consists, basically, in a two step process: in a first step, CH₄ reacts with water steam, ($\text{CH}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \leftrightarrow \text{CO} + 3\text{H}_2$) over different catalysts at a temperature of about 750°C-800°C, (endothermic), giving a mixture of CO and H₂ with relative CO/H₂ ratio near to 0.33 (this mixture is normally referred as synthesis gas). In a second step, CO is further oxidized to CO₂ leading to more H₂ ($\text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2$). Besides the SMR, we should also remark an alternative process, called *Dry Reforming of Methane* (DRM) ($\text{CH}_4 + \text{CO}_2 \leftrightarrow 2\text{CO} + 2\text{H}_2$, endothermic)[6]. The main advantage of this process is the possibility of using a big number of reserves

of natural gas where together with CH₄, important amounts of CO₂ are found, and through this process the CO₂ will not be emitted into the atmosphere. Furthermore, in this reaction a CO/H₂ ratio near to 1.0 is produced, what it is interesting for the transformation of this “synthesis gas” into chemicals [7] or fuels such as methanol or gasoline [8].

Reforming reactions (steam and dry) have been conventionally operated with nickel/alumina catalysts, at temperatures above 800°C, due to the endothermic character of the global reactions. The main problem of these reactions is the deactivation of the catalyst due to the formation of coke fibers [9]. This coke deposition, that it is specially observed in the dry reforming process [3] can be originated from a direct cracking of methane ($\text{CH}_4 = \text{C} + 2\text{H}_2$), or through a Boudouard reaction ($2\text{CO} = \text{C} + \text{CO}_2$), or even by a direct reduction of CO with H₂. It should be remarked that although use of noble metals (Pt, Ru, Rh) in the composition of catalysts leads to a higher activity and a decrease in the deactivation process [9-12], from an industrial point of view, nickel is preferentially used because is much more economically competitive.

The coke formation on these catalysts have been correlated, by several authors with the morphology, size and distribution of nickel particles onto the oxide acting as support [13,14], and in particular it has been assumed that is originated by a reaction “structurally sensible” [15-17]. In this context, a group of authors have proposed to obtain highly dispersed nickel particles using, for example, a process called “solid phase crystallization”, where Ni particles are “extracted” from solids with perovskite-type structure (i.e such as LaNiO₃) by a treatment under reducing conditions [18,19].

Another way to improve catalytic behavior of systems based on Ni has focused on the modification of support characteristics, and related with that, on the nature of

metal-support interaction [20-22]. In this topic, several cases such as Ni supported on ZrO₂ [23,24] or Ce-ZrO₂ [25,26] have been studied, presenting high stability and activity, what authors have claimed to be due to the existence of Strong Metal Support Interactions (SMSI).

In the context of the aspects exposed above, here we report the synthesis of several catalysts based on Ni, and use of CeO₂ as support, as this oxide present itself certain activity in the methane steam reforming reaction, and tends to oxidize the coke formed during reaction [27]. We have developed a preparation method, that alternatively to the conventional methods (impregnation, precipitation ionic exchange), allows to obtain catalysts with a wide range of Ni loading (5-30%), showing in all the cases relatively small particles (5-15 nm), with a narrow size distribution, well crystallized and homogeneously dispersed on the support.

Experimental

Catalyst preparation

Ni-Ceria system was prepared by combustion synthesis. Although this method has been mostly used for the preparation of different materials such as ceramics [28,29], has been also used in the catalysis field, especially to improve the surface area of single phase multi-component materials, such as perovskites [30]. Up to our knowledge, few works have been dedicated to the preparation of “conventional” M/M'O_x catalysts (a metallic phase dispersed onto a support) with metals as Pd or Ru [31,32], presenting different variables of the combustion method. Also, there is a work [33] where is used a method very similar to our synthesis with Ni and Ce, but it reported to obtain a single phase Ce_{1-x}Ni_xO_y.

Although a description of the method has been previously presented by us [21], basically it consists in the preparation of an aqueous solution containing $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (from Aldrich) as metal/support precursors, together with a reducing agent acting as fuel (citric acid in our case). This solution is first evaporated slowly at 150°C , and when a dried gel is formed, temperature is quickly increased up to 500°C . Then an auto-ignited explosive reaction occurs, leaving a solid with a brownish colour. After cooling down to room temperature (RT), the solid thus obtained was calcined in synthetic air at 750°C , that assuring that no carbonaceous residues remain in the sample.

In the work reported in this article, we have prepared two sets of catalysts: First a set with different Ni loading (7, 13 and 26%) and a second set with different ratio of the component acting as fuel (citric acid). This second set has been prepared as several works [34] report that this parameter affects to the crystallinity of the phases (i.e here NiO and CeO_2) formed. Table 1 summarizes the different catalysts prepared.

Temperature Programmed Reduction (TPR)

TPR experiments were done on a H_2/Ar mixture (5% H_2 , 50ml/min flow) from room temperature up to 750°C , with a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. The experimental conditions were chosen to assure that no peak coalescence occurs [35]. A thermal conductivity detector (TCD), previously calibrated using CuO, and a mass spectrometer in line with the TCD, calibrated with reference mixtures, were used to detect variations of H_2 concentration, and possible sub-products formation.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD)

SEM images were obtained in a Hitachi S-5200 microscopy, with a field emission filament, using an accelerating voltage of 5kV. X-ray diffractograms, were recorded in a Siemens D-501 equipment, with a Bragg-Brentano configuration, using Cu K α ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$). Spectra were collected in the range $2\theta = 20-80^\circ$, with a step of 0.05° and an acquisition time of 1s for each point.

Catalytic Activity Tests.

Reaction was carried out at room temperature in a fixed-bed tubular reactor, using 20 mg of catalyst between two pompons of quartz wool. The CH₄ and CO₂ or H₂O reactants were mixed at a ratio of 1 diluted in He (10:10:80 in vol.). Calcined samples were heated put in contact with the reaction mixture, without any further treatment, and heated from room temperature up to 750°C at 1°C/min rate, holding the samples at 750°C during 12h, and cooled down to room temperature in the same reaction mixture. In all the cases, the experiments have been carried out using a gas hourly space velocity (GHSV) of 300,000 L/kg·h (20 mg of sample). Analysis of reactants and products were done by a Gas Chromatograph (Varian CP-3800) with a Thermal Conductivity Sensor and two in series columns (Molecular Sieve, 5A, Porapak Q). As mentioned before, reactivity tests presented here correspond to unreduced samples, although reaction mixture causes the reduction of the NiO to Ni⁰ at temperatures of ca. 500-650 °C. There are several works (ref?) in the literature that pointed out the influence of a pre-reduction of the samples in H₂ in the reactivity of this type of catalysts. In fact, a detailed study of this treatment on the same samples will be presented shortly.

X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS)

Samples were pelletized and introduced in the analysis chamber of a Leybold LH-10 spectrometer, after evacuation at 150°C at 10^{-7} torr in the prechamber. Acquisition of the spectra was done using Al K α radiation (1486.6 eV) with 20 mA of anode current and 12 kV of potential acceleration. It is important to note that all the spectra correspond to “ex-situ” samples (calcined, post-reaction), keeping the samples under reactant gases at room temperature until few minutes before their introduction into the analysis equipment. Although this exposure into the atmosphere would cause the oxidation of the Ce³⁺ ions (if formed in the case of post-reaction samples) and possibly the partial reoxidation of Ni⁰ to NiO, the protocol ensures a minimal contamination of samples with spurious carbon and/or formation of carbonates, what results in an appropriate quantification of exposed Ni, the main objective of this set of experiments.

Results and Discussion.

XRD diagrams of the different Ni/CeO₂ catalysts are shown in Fig 1. As can be seen, in all the cases all the peaks observed correspond to the cubic phases of CeO₂ (fluorite type) and NiO. With respect to the NiO peaks, they are observed clearly in the NiCe26-ac25 sample, but their intensity diminishes, as expected, with the Ni loading. In the case of the samples of Set 2, no significant differences are observed either in the CeO₂ or NiO peaks.

A detailed analysis of the broadening of the peaks, using the Scherrer formula, and the corresponding calculated sizes for NiO and CeO₂ nanocrystal is presented in Table 2. The calculated particle size values from XRD indicate that the crystallite size (crystalline dominium) of CeO₂ slightly increases when the Ni loading decreases (SET

1), from about 10 nm in NiCe26-ac25 to 25 nm in NiCe7-ac25. Changes in the metallic loading has almost no effect in the sizes of NiO crystallites in this SET-1, presenting in all the cases values of ca. 15 nm mean diameter. In the case of samples of SET 2, NiO sizes present similar values for NiCe13-ac25 and NiCe13-ac15 (ca. 14 nm) but slightly bigger for NiCe13-ac10. Data of NiO and CeO₂ crystallite size of samples after reaction offset have been also incorporated in Table 2. In all the cases, a significant increase of CeO₂ crystallite size is observed, specially, for samples that originally presented lower sizes. On the contrary NiO particles (now in the form of metallic nickel, Ni⁰) present similar values for almost all samples, and only experiment a significant increase in the sample with higher Ni content (NiCe26-ac25). In Table 2 we have also incorporated BET values of the samples prepared. These values vary from ca. 10 m²/g to ca. 25 m²/g, in the range expected to CeO₂ samples after calcination at 600°C. The obtained values do not present a clear tendency either with metallic loading (SET 1) or with reducing/oxidizer ratio (SET 2).

SEM images corresponding to samples of Set 1 and Set 2 have been included in Figure 2 and Figure 3. In all the images we can observe the presence of small particles, well formed and defined, that present a higher contrast. These particles have been confirmed using STEM and Backscattering images that correspond to the NiO phases. These particles are in general cubic shaped, well faceted (see Figure2) with sizes that are around 15 nm, and are homogeneously distributed across the support surface (Figure 3). The density of these particles diminishes with the Ni Loading. It is also important to note that the particle size values observed in the images nearly resembles those obtained from XRD calculations.

After calcination and as part of the characterization, all the catalysts have been submitted to temperature programmed reduction profiles, registering the hydrogen consumption vs temperature. TPR profiles for the samples of set 1 and set 2 are plotted in the Figure 4. In the plot of set 1 is also included, as reference, the TPR profile of a commercial NiO green with big particles size (micrometer order).

TPRs of prepared samples present, in all cases broad peaks, with reduction maxima that are well below that found on the massive NiO (420°C). There is no noticeable changes in the maxima temperature with the Ni loading or the oxidizing/fuel ratio. The H₂ consumptions, expressed in micromols/g of catalyst are detailed in Table 3. In all the cases, the consumption obtained corresponds to that expected for the reduction of the NiO phase to metallic Ni⁰. Nevertheless, is also noticeable that, although in the error range, some excess of hydrogen is observed in all the cases. This is reasonable, and as discussed in extension elsewhere [36,37], would correspond to the surface reduction of the CeO₂ particles, occurring at the same time than NiO. This fact is easily understood in terms of a “spillover” effect from hydrogen adsorbed on Ni particles to the CeO₂ surface.

Samples have been also analyzed by XPS, in order to have more information on the amount of Ni exposed in the surface, and its modification after reaction conditions. Results from XPS analysis for samples of SET 2 are presented in Fig 5, for Ni2p and C1s, and a complete resume of peaks areas for all the significant elements detected is presented in Table 4. Ce3d signals, not presented, show in all cases features characteristics of Ce⁴⁺. This is easily understood due to the fact that all the samples are “ex situ”, and have been exposed at the atmosphere. It is well known [38] that in CeO₂,

and, specially, on high surface area samples, even short exposures with O₂ (10⁻² torr, 5 min) would cause the total oxidation of Ce³⁺ ions (if formed during reaction) to Ce⁴⁺.

Regarding the areas of Ni, it is clear that in all the cases the Ni content detected by XPS is well below their theoretical values, even considering a solid solution of formula NiCe_xO_y. It should be remarked that the observed signal of Ni/Ce ratios have been transformed into “Effective Ni loadings”, taking into account Ni particle size and geometric factors according to possible particle orientation into the support. This lower content of surface Ni, observed in all the samples can be easily explained in terms of the high temperatures that microscopically would occur during synthesis of materials, and the well known SMSI effects of Ni/CeO₂ systems [21,39], what finally would lead to the burial of Ni into the CeO₂ and/or “decoration” of Ni particles with the ceria.

Regarding the comparison of the different samples in SET 2, we can observe that while ac-10 and ac-15 samples present a high percentage of Ni exposed at the surface (ca. 10-13%, next to the theoretical value), sample ac-25 present significantly lower Ni exposed (8.4%). Moreover, these percentages of Ni observed at the surface decrease after reaction with CO₂+CH₄ in all the samples, but the decrease is more accused in the ac-25 sample (from 8.4% to ca. 4.4%). The shape of Ni2p peak corresponds in all the cases to NiO, except in ac-15 after reaction, where a small fraction of Ni could be in reduced state. Nevertheless, because samples are “ex-situ”, we may not consider this a significant characteristic due to a different chemical behavior of this sample.

Finally, is also worth of noting that, after reaction offset, all the samples present a significant amount of C, consisting of a well defined single peak centered at ca. 284.5

eV, what it is consistent with a nanofiber or nanotube carbon type, according with data observed by SEM (see below).

Reactivity data, for the dry reforming of methane ($\text{CH}_4 + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{CO} + 2\text{H}_2$) are plotted, for all the catalysts prepared, in Figure 6. Although not presented, in all the cases, the samples began to be active after 550°C, and its activity increases with temperature up to 750°C.

For samples in SET 1 and SET 2, they present a behavior very similar: after the maximum temperature is reached, the samples experienced, at isotherm conditions, a slight decrease in their activity, although direct comparison of conversions is not straight forward between different samples due to different loadings, atoms exposed, etc. For instance, when comparing samples in SET 1 is clear that a tendency exists, and samples with higher loading present higher conversions. Nevertheless, that correlation ($\text{NiCe}_{26}\text{-ac}_{25} > \text{NiCe}_{13}\text{-ac}_{25} > \text{NiCe}_7\text{-ac}_{25}$) do not longer exist when samples in SET 2 are compared: in this case three samples with the same Ni loading present very different conversion values. As can be seen, samples prepared with lower oxidizer/reducing ratio present higher activity than $\text{NiCe}_{13}\text{-ac}_{25}$, although a maximum seems to occur for $\text{NiCe}_{13}\text{-ac}_{15}$, where besides its high activity, is remarkable the good stability observed.

In order to overcome the apparent diversity of conversions, we have calculated the corresponding TOF values for each sample. Although TOF values should take into account the number of active sites (in principle atoms of Ni exposed) for each sample, the estimation of this number is difficult in Ni/CeO₂ catalysts: for instance, chemisorption methods give no conclusive results, as H₂ adsorption is normally overestimated due to the well known adsorption process in the CeO₂ support [40], and

CO chemisorption is highly influenced on Ni particles by the presence of different crystallographic faces and/or defects.

Therefore, we have calculated the number of active sites considering the effective Ni loading from observed XPS signals (Table 4) and the estimated number of atoms in the surface (dispersion) taking into account the mean size value of the particles, obtained by XRD. A summary of these calculations have been incorporated in Table 5. From data in this table, is now evident that in all the cases TOF values are practically the same, considering the error margins and therefore the observed differences in activity are mostly related with differences in the total number of active sites exposed, that are related with the effective Ni loading (number of particles exposed in the surface) and the dispersion of these Ni particles (thus inherent to their size). Only a minor difference is observed in the NiCe26-ac25 sample, presenting slightly lower TOF values, what could be related with the fact that this is the only sample where a significant increase in particle size was observed after reaction offset (Table3).

One of the main problems found on these type of catalysts, as discussed in the introduction, is the possible coke and carbon nanofiber formation, what may lead to an eventual deactivation of the catalyst. This is quite evident in the XPS results (see Fig 6 and table 4), where carbon signal is noticeable and significant even after only five minutes of operation. As can be seen, although it seems there is a tendency in the amount of carbon formed, (specially in the case of Set 2, where a bigger differences were observed), it should be remarked that data correspond with samples just after reaction offset, and macroscopic amounts of carbon were detected on all the samples after reaction (12 hours), in some cases almost blocking the reactor tube. A SEM study

of these post-reaction samples, after 12 hours running is presented in Figure 7. From the images in Figure 7 is clear that after dry reforming reaction, all the carbon detected is in the form of nanofibers. These fibers present a diameter between 50-80nm and a variable length, although normally are bigger than one micron. Oxidation experiments done on these post-reaction samples have evidenced the formation of CO₂ as the only detected product, and in any case H₂O has been detected. This seems to indicate that the fibers formed respond to a “nanotube” type, and no coke (C_xH_y) carbon formation could be inferred.

It is evident that for practical applications, a high activity and selectivity is desired, and that high values should remain stable as longer as possible. This seems to be the case, at least for some of the catalysts here prepared. Moreover, the catalysts present also very high activity and stability even under concentrated conditions. Nevertheless, we have noticed that these catalysts produced a considerable amount of carbon nanofibers under operating conditions. Although this type of carbon do not seem to induce a deactivation of the catalyst, it could represent a serious problem for industrial application as it may lead to a pressure drop, or even to a blocking of the reactor. A further study of the factors that affect to this carbon formation, its extent and the possible optimization of the catalyst to overcome this problem will be presented shortly.

Conclusions

Several catalysts with Ni/CeO₂ general composition have been prepared, within a wide range of Ni loadings (7-26%), using the “combustion synthesis” and starting from Ni and Ce nitrates.

Combustion Synthesis have resulted in a simple, effective and reliable method to prepare catalysts of the type M/MO_x in a wide range of loadings, leading to few nanometers particles (ca. 13-15nm), quite homogeneous in size and well distributed over the support surface. The main advantages of the method are the simplicity, control of the final stoichiometry and the economic feasibility for a large scale production, as no complicated equipment is necessary nor separation process are needed neither high price precursors should be used.

All the catalysts present two very well differentiated phases: NiO and CeO₂, without any other impurity or even carbon residual found after calcinations of the samples at 750°C. The catalysts present after this calcinations process a surface area of ca. 20 m²/g, what is notable for those calcinations temperatures. It should be noted that similar surface areas are obtained when high surface area CeO₂ (i.e 120 to 200 m²/g) are calcined at those temperatures.

The catalysts have been tested for dry reforming of methane, considering two factors in the preparation; metallic loading and oxidizer/reducing agent ratio. All the catalysts present similar TOF values, that according with the conditions used could result in conversion and selectivity close to thermodynamic values.

With respect to the reducer/oxidizer ratio, we have found that this parameter seems to affect specially in the number of Ni particles exposed in the catalysts, increasing it with lower ratios, what make more active catalysts.

Although the activity stability shown here is maintained by the catalysts even after been working at concentrated conditions (pure CH₄ and CO₂) for more than two weeks, a severe carbon deposition have been observed in the form of narrow and long

nanofibers, what may result in a serious drawback for industrial application of these catalysts.

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Figure Captions

Figure 1. X-Ray diffraction diagrams (XRD) of prepared Ni/CeO₂ systems. Symbols correspond with observed phases: ▲, NiO, ◇ CeO₂.

Figure 2. High magnification microscopy images (FEG-SEM) of NiCe26-ac25 sample. Left and right: Detail of cubic shaped NiO particles.

Figure 3. Microscopy images FEG-SEM of prepared catalysts. Above, SET 1: NiCe26-ac25 (left), NiCe13-ac25 (center), NiCe7-ac25 (right). Below, SET 2: NiCe13-ac25 (left), NiCe13-ac15 (center), NiCe13-ac10 (right).

Figure 4. Temperature Programmed Reduction (TPR) of prepared samples: Left SET 1 (commercial NiO green included). Right, SET 2.

Figure 5. XPS spectra for Ni2p_{3/2} (left) and C1s regions (right) of samples after calcination (dots) and post-reaction treatments (solid line). A) SET 1. B) SET 2.

Figure 6. CH₄ conversion at T=750°C for samples of set 1 and set 2.

Figure 7. FEG-SEM images of samples after dry reforming of methane reaction. a) NiCe13-ac15, b) NiCe26-ac25, c) NiCe26-ac25 (Backscattering).

Table 1. Different Ni/CeO₂ catalysts prepared by combustion method.

	Sample Name	Metallic loading (weight %)	oxid./red. ratio
SET 1	NiCe26-ac25	Ni, 26%	1 : 2.5
	NiCe13-ac25	Ni, 13%	1 : 2.5
	NiCe7-ac25	Ni, 7%	1 : 2.5
SET 2	NiCe13-ac10	Ni, 13%	1 : 1.0
	NiCe13-ac15	Ni, 13%	1 : 1.5
	NiCe13-ac25	Ni, 13%	1 : 2.5

Table 2. Microstructural data of the Ni/CeO₂ samples.

	Sample	DRX Crystallite Size (calcined)		DRX Crystallite Size (Reaction offset)		N ₂ BET (m ² /gr)
		CeO ₂	NiO	CeO ₂	Ni ⁰	
SET 1	NiCe26-ac25	10	13	22	28	16
	NiCe13-ac25	15	13	21	15	11
	NiCe7-ac25	25	15	25	16	10
SET 2	NiCe13-ac25	15	13	21	15	11
	NiCe13-ac15	12	12	21	12	25
	NiCe13-ac10	21	21	25	21	22

Table 3. Experimental Hydrogen consumption from TPR profiles of Figure 3. Estimated data for reduction of NiO phase and excess corresponding to surface reduction of CeO₂ have been also included.

Sample	H ₂ consumed ($\mu\text{mol/g}$)	H ₂ (Ni ²⁺ →Ni ⁰) ($\mu\text{mol/g}$)	H ₂ (Ce ⁴⁺ →Ce ³⁺) ($\mu\text{mol/g}$)	
SET 1	NiCe26-ac25	4180	4050	130
	NiCe13-ac25	2480	2390	90
	NiCe7-ac25	1370	1310	60
SET 2	NiCe13-ac25	2480	2390	90
	NiCe13-ac15	2470	2390	80
	NiCe13-ac10	2505	2390	115

Table 4. Observed Ni/Ce and C/Ce atomic ratios from XPS Ni2p_{3/2}, Ce3d and C1s signals for samples of SET1 and SET2 after calcination and at the beginning of reaction.

Sample	Ni loading, % wt.	XPS signal Ni/Ce		XPS signal C/Ce		Effective Ni loading, % wt.	
		Calcined	CH ₄ +CO ₂	Calcined	CH ₄ +CO ₂	Calcined	CH ₄ +CO ₂
SET 1							
NiCe26-ac25	26	0.42	0.18	0	12.9	18.6	13.4
NiCe13-ac25	13	0.19	0.10	0	1.3	8.4	4.4

NiCe7-ac25	7	0.11	0.08	0	0	5.0	3.7
SET 2							
NiCe13-ac10	13	0.25	0.22	0	1.6	13.0	11.4
NiCe13-ac15	13	0.28	0.18	0	2.4	10.2	8.0
NiCe13-ac25	13	0.19	0.10	0	1.3	8.4	4.4

Table 5. Calculated TOF values for reactivity of samples using dispersion and effective nickel loading estimated from XRD and XPS data respectively.

Sample	Dispersion %	Effective Ni loading, %	Active Ni sites Mols (x10⁶)	CH₄ Mols converted/s (x10⁶) @ 750°C, 5 min	TOF, s⁻¹
SET 1					
NiCe26-ac25	4.0	13.4	1.8	6.2	3.4
NiCe13-ac25	7.7	4.4	1.2	5.1	4.3
NiCe7-ac25	7.5	3.7	1.0	4.3	4.3
SET 2					
NiCe13-ac10	5.5	11.4	2.1	8.2	3.9
NiCe13-ac15	9.2	8.0	2.5	11.1	4.4
NiCe13-ac25	7.7	4.4	1.2	5.1	4.3

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

FIGURE 5

FIGURE 6

FIGURE 7

